

ANALYSIS OF EFFICIENCY INDICATORS IN THE FINANCING MECHANISM OF STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES

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One of its important financial levers is the introduction of a system of assessment, efficiency and monitoring of the effectiveness of the executive body of enterprises, in which the state owns a share in the market relations. This is KPI - *English*, which is widely used in world practice Key Performance Indicators - (*key performance indicator*) - important indicators to be performed are used. In fact, KPIs **are an important indicator of efficiency** It is a quantitative measure of the evaluation criteria ¹used to determine

ABSTRACT

One of the important steps in the financing mechanism of state-owned enterprises is the assessment of the effectiveness of joint-stock companies with limited share capital, limited liability and additional liability companies, state-owned enterprises. The state is economically interested in ensuring the minimum efficiency of their financial and economic activities in order to ensure financial stability in the enterprises in which they have a share. Of course, the relationship between the introduction of performance indicators in enterprises with state share, its analysis and regulation is a comprehensive process. This article focuses on these issues.

the effectiveness of the activities of members of joint-stock companies, limited liability companies and executive bodies of state-owned enterprises, which have a state share in the charter capital, and has been widely used in Uzbekistan since March 2016.

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¹<https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/ru/kpi>.

in ensuring the minimum efficiency of their financial and economic activities in order to ensure financial stability in the enterprises in which they have a share.

Literature review

In the context of market relations, a lot of research has been conducted on the application of performance indicators as a means of financial management of the state. In particular, in the financing mechanism of state-owned enterprises joint-stock companies with state share in the charter capital, limited liability and additional liability companies, research on the effectiveness of state-owned enterprises Armstong M., Beron A., Druker P.F., Lezhnev.O, Kaloshina.L, Eremina. G.A., Jemchugov A.M., Kaplan R., Norton D., Klochkov A., Redchenko K., Chiapello E., Lebas M. Kabilar, ²as well as Uzbek

scientists T.Malikov, O.Olimjanov, S.Elmirzaev carried out by. In particular, M.Armstong and A.Beron in their research created a theoretical basis for the use of performance indicators that are important in the organization of financial management of enterprises, P.Druker in his research studied methods of application and analysis of performance indicators, A.Jemchugov in his research evaluates as balanced indicators, while A. Klochkov showed a system for evaluating important performance indicators for enterprises, as well as Kaplan R., D. Norton also reveals the differences between performance indicators and the characteristics of their application.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2015 " On the introduction of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state participation" **Resolution** No. 207 stipulates that the management of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state participation should consider these issues to ensure the introduction of performance evaluation criteria , and despite the fact that this process has been used in the Uzbek economy for the past 5 years. there are also specific problems in implementing the process. This indicates that the need for scientific research remains high with the application of key performance indicators in state-owned enterprises.

Research Methodology

This scientific article, aimed at monitoring the activities of state-owned

to Management Information // Working Paper (Revised Third Draft), August 2001, p. 3-10.

² Armstong M., Beron A. Upravlenie rezultativnostyu. M.: Alpina Publisher, 2014. 240 p., Druker P.F. Effective upravlyayushchiy. - M.: Book Chamber International, 2004. - 268 p., Oleg Lejnev, Lyudmila Kaloshina. [Postroenie kompleksnyx sistem upravleniya zdorovom promyshlennyx holdingov s ispolzovaniem Business Studio](https://www.businessstudio.ru/articles/biznes_protsesty/) https://www.businessstudio.ru/articles/biznes_protsesty/., Eremina Galina Anatolevna. Klyuchevye pokazateli efektyvnosti kak instrument upravleniya organizatsiy. Internet magazine "NAUKOVEDENIE" <http://naukovedenie.ru>. Volume 7, №5 (September - October 2015) ., A.M. Jemchugov. SBALANSIROVANNAYA SYSTEM POKAZATELEY. NEDOSTATKI ILI NEPRAVILNOE ISPOLZOVANIE? Journal "Problems of Economics and Management", № 8 (36) - 2014. , Kaplan R., Norton D. Sbalansirovannaya system pokazateley, izmeryayushchix efektyvnost. // Series «Classic Harvard Business Review», Review of company results. M.: Alpina business box, 2007. p. 123-144. , Klochkov A. KPIs and staff motivation. M.: Eksmo, 2010. 170 p., Redchenko K. Pokazatelnoe nesoglasie: Balanced Scorecard and Tableau De Board [Electronic resource]. - URL: <http://www.management.com.ua/strategy/str046.html> ., Peter F. Druker. Management practices. Per. s ang. M.: Mann, Ivanov and Ferber, 2014. 416 p., Chiapello E., Lebas M. The Tableau de Bord, a French Approach

enterprises, ensuring their competitiveness, assessing the responsibility of the executive bodies in research. Of course, if the dialectical method is studied in relation to the economic indicators used in the activities of state-owned enterprises, the scientific and theoretical analysis of approaches to financing state-owned enterprises based on theoretical observation and a logical approach. Scientific conclusions are made based on the methods of synthesis and analysis of important indicators of efficiency, based on the deductive or inductive approach, which allows to study the factors influencing the important indicators of efficiency from bottom to top and vice versa.

Analysis and results

In the 80s and 90s of the last century, the results of scientific and theoretical research on the development and application of a new system of economic indicators as one of the important factors in the effective management of enterprises in the world economy began to be put into practice. For example, Management by Objectives, created by professors at Harvard Business School in the United States in the 80s and 90s of the twentieth century. that is "The ability to anticipate the results of their work and ways to achieve them A "Balanced Scorecard System" ³has been developed to set targets for the implementation of its mission and strategic objectives and to disclose information on the status of their implementation to stakeholders. has been used in many countries for nearly forty years.

such enterprises, makes effective use of general and specific research methods of scientific

of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 27, 2020 No PF-6096 " [On measures to accelerate the reform of state-owned enterprises and privatization of state assets](#) ", as well as economic societies and state unitary enterprises Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 28, 2015 " On the introduction of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state participation" According to Resolution No. 207, ensuring the efficiency of economic activity of enterprises with state participation is a priority.

According to the above-mentioned normative legal acts, the state had a share in the charter fund joint stock companies, limited liability companies and to state enterprises, as well as *Due to the fact that the state share in the charter capital of joint-stock companies belongs to public administration and local authorities, state enterprises and institutions, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Fund for Reconstruction and Development, it is mandatory to introduce them in such companies.*

³<https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/ru/kpi>.

Table 1.

Introduction of key performance indicators in state-owned enterprises in Uzbekistan and its results ⁴

№	Years	Level of application											
		High		Enough		Medium		Not enough		Past		Unsatisfactory	
		Soni	%	Soni	%	Soni	%	Soni	%	Soni	%	Soni	%
1.	2019	857	46.3	158	8.5	206	11.1	305	16.5	107	5.8	219	11.8
2.	2020	802	43.0	196	10.5	231	12.4	277	14.9	125	6.7	232	12.5
3.	2021	606	30	128	6.3	156	7.7	191	9.5	65	3.2	871	43.2

⁴ Uzbekistan Republic State assets management based on agency data. <https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/uz/kpi>.

As noted above, since the first quarter of 2016 in the economy of Uzbekistan, the management of state-owned joint-stock companies and other business entities has been implementing performance evaluation criteria.

The analysis of the data in Table 1 shows that in 2019-2021, the level of application of key performance indicators in state-owned enterprises in the country increased quantitatively, but the number of enterprises used at a high level decreased to 251 in 2021 compared to 2019. While

the number has decreased by 30 in the years under analysis, the number of enterprises used unsatisfactorily has increased to 652 in 2021 compared to 2019. It follows that despite the fact that the enterprises of the republic have 5 years of experience in the application of important performance indicators, the implementation of this process is unsatisfactory. This, in turn, leads to the conclusion that the efficiency of economic activity of state-owned enterprises is not good.

Table 2.

Regional analysis of the introduction of key performance indicators in ⁵state-owned enterprises in Uzbekistan (As of 01.12.2020)

№	Name of regions	C is the number of enterprises that need to introduce key performance indicators	C is the number of enterprises that have introduced key performance indicators	
			Soni	Percentage
	Tashkent city	507	232	46
	Surkhandarya region	50	26	52
	Bukhara region	105	53	50
	Andijan region	102	92	90
	Jizzakh region	75	73	97
	Namangan region	97	90	93
	Syrdarya region	75	71	95
	Samarkand region	144	101	70
	Navoi region	77	62	81
	Kashkadarya region	191	163	85
	Khorezm region	57	47	82
	Tashkent region	169	168	98
	The Republic of Karakalpakstan	89	82	92
	Fergana region	109	47	82

⁵ Uzbekistan Republic State assets management based on agency data. <https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/uz/kpi>.

If we pay attention to the analysis of the introduction of key performance indicators in state-owned enterprises in Uzbekistan by region, 168 out of 169 enterprises in Tashkent region (98%), 73 out of 75 enterprises in Jizzakh region (97%), 75 enterprises in Syrdarya region. 71 (95%) have been implemented, and in addition to the effective organization of

work in this area, the implementation of key performance indicators in Tashkent, Surkhandarya and Bukhara regions is an average of 50%, which is insufficient.

In terms of content and structure, the key performance indicators (EPIs) in state-owned enterprises consist of two parts, namely, the main and additional indicators:

Table 3.

Features of key performance indicators used in state-owned enterprises in Uzbekistan

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№	S naming of important indicators of efficiency	C. Properties of important indicators of efficiency
1.	Return on assets (profitability)	Enterprise financial - economic activities profitability (or damage) level shows
2.	Net revenue forecast indicator completion	the products produced by the enterprise, the services rendered, the total amount of money received from the work performed
3.	Net profit (loss) forecast indicator completion	the final result of the enterprise's activities for the reporting period, as well as how useful it is to carry out this type of activity
4.	Developers remove from power use coefficients	Indicates the level of utilization of production capacity of the enterprise on the basis of the ratio of the volume of actual production, the maximum production capacity (excluding leased and conserved capacity)
5.	Coverage ratio (solvency)	Indicates the ability of the enterprise not only to successfully sell the finished product and timely settle accounts with debtors, but also to cover short-term liabilities based on the assessment of other elements of current (current) assets
6.	Financial independence coefficients	The ratio of own and short-term borrowings (in the current financial independence) determines the degree of security of repayment of borrowed funds from their own sources
7.	Dividend calculation	Represents how much of an enterprise's net profit is directed to ordinary shares as dividend payments.
8.	Export parameters completion (defined	It is calculated on the basis of the percentage of the actually achieved indicators of the approved export

⁶ Compiled by the author on the basis of current regulations.

	assignment relatively percent)	parameters to the established forecast indicators
9.	Localization indicator fulfillment	Calculated on the basis of the percentage of actual implementation of projects identified for the current period in the approved network and (or) regional localization programs
10.	Investment programs completion	Calculated on the basis of the percentage of funds actually disbursed under the investment program to the target (forecast) set by the approved investment program
11.	From foreign currency independence coefficients	The ratio of imports to exports shows that payments for imported goods are offset by product exports
12.	Return on Total Shareholders Return (TSR)	Total share income. This indicator represents the value of shareholders' income as a result of changes in stock quotes and the calculation of dividends on the stock exchange

In addition, additional performance indicators are used to describe the economic and financial condition of state-owned enterprises, including " Earnings Before Interest, Taxes", "Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Other Interest Payments". Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation & Amortization "(CIR - Cost Income Ratio), " Return on Capital Employed "(ROCE), " Return on Capital Employed " Return on Equity ", " Absolute liquidity ratio ", " Daily turnover of accounts payable ", " Daily turnover of receivables ", " Depreciation rate of fixed assets ", " Renewal ratio of fixed assets ", " Labor productivity ", " Fund return", "Share of innovative products in total sales", "Total expenses of the enterprise The share of expenditures on innovative activities ", " Employee Unemployment Ratio ", " Indicator of Performance Indicators of Production Capacity " ⁷, etc., which also serve to

effectively organize the production of enterprises and reflect the state of financial indicators.

⁷ <https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/uz/kpi>.

Table 4.

Analysis of key performance indicators of additional efficiency in JSC "Quartz" for 2020⁸

N ^o	Indicators	Weight	Forecast (target indicator for 2020)	Real indicator 2020	Percentage of completion	SMK
	A	V	S	D	E	$F = ExB / 100$
1	Depreciation rate of fixed assets	10	0.68	0.73	93.2	9.3
2	Fixed asset renewal ratio	8	0.2	0.013	6.6	0.5
3	Labor productivity	20	87 423	132 909	152.0	30.4
4	Fund efficiency	15	3.06	5.23	171.0	25.6
5	Production capacity utilization factor	20	1.0	1.0	100.0	20.0
6	Energy efficiency (energy costs relative to the cost of the product)	7	0.23	0.219	104.9	7.3
7	Staff training costs are calculated per employee	5	12 421	54 736	440.7	22.0
8	Effectiveness of staff turnover	5	0.99	0.98	101.0	5.1
9	Execution of export parameters (in% of cash flows)	10	87.3	125.1	143.3	14.3
10.	Total:	100				134.7

⁸ Calculated by the author on the basis of financial indicators of JSC "Quartz".

If we see this in the economic and financial activities of JSC "Quartz", which belongs to the category of enterprises with state participation. The main indicators of efficiency of the enterprise for 2020 serve to determine the efficiency of the executive body of the enterprise. This is stated in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2015 "On the introduction of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of state-owned joint-stock companies and other business entities." **According to the requirements of the "REGULATIONS on the criteria for financial stability, solvency, capacity utilization, export-import, localization and investment programs, energy efficiency and other indicators of efficiency are important indicators, and it is of high economic importance to determine efficiency by setting a minimum level of these indicators.**

At the same time, in our opinion, it is expedient to apply important indicators of efficiency in state-owned enterprises and further improve its criteria. That is, in accordance with paragraph 27 OF THE "REGULATIONS on the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state share", the effectiveness of the executive body is recognized as follows:

If the sum of the efficiency is less than 40% - unsatisfactory;

If the sum of the indicators of efficiency is from 40% to 60% (including this level) - at a low level;

If the sum of the indicators of efficiency is from 60% to 80% (including this level) - not enough;

If the sum of the indicators of efficiency is from 80% to 90% (including this level) - on average;

assessing the effectiveness of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state participation " approved by Resolution No. 207, the basis for assessing the level of financial activity of the joint-stock company is good.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Indeed, not only in state-owned enterprises, but also in the financial activities of other enterprises engaged in entrepreneurial activities, net income, net profit, cost reduction,

If the sum of the indicators of efficiency is from 90% to 100% (including this level) - sufficient;

If the sum of the efficiency indicators exceeds 100 percent - at a high level.

However, this criterion does not take into account the level of state share in the enterprise. Therefore, if the state's share in the enterprise is less than 30%, it is advisable to set an unsatisfactory limit of 25 or less.

In addition, as an important indicator of key efficiency, the indicator "Daily turnover of receivables" was transferred to the additional efficiency indicator, combining the additional efficiency indicators "Fund efficiency" and "Capacity utilization rate" and renamed it "Fund utilization efficiency" and its weight. It is advisable to define Because the ratio of "daily turnover of receivables" does not have a significant negative impact on the financial performance of the enterprise, at the same time, the indicators of "Fund efficiency" and "Capacity utilization ratio" are close in content.

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